

Synthesis, Antibacterial and Antifungal Activities of 2,4-Dimethyl-3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines and related Benzothiazolylguanidines

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The compounds containing thiadiazole and benzothiazole rings have been found to exhibit broad spectrum anti-bacterial activity. Derivatives of 1,2,4-thiadiazole and 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines exhibit antibacterial and fungicidal properties¹. A series of 2-(benzalhydrazinocarbonylmethylthio)benzothiazoles and their 2-azetidones also exhibit moderate to good antibacterial and antifungal activities². In view of the above facts, it was thought pertinent to synthesise some new thiadiazolidines and related benzothiazolyl guanidines for their antibacterial and antifungal activities. The two series of compounds were prepared to study the effect of changing the thiadiazolidine structure to a benzothiazolyl structure on the antibacterial and antifungal activities.

The 2,4-dimethyl-3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (1a-1) were prepared by the nitrous acid oxidation of *N*-methyl-*N'*-arylthioureas and the thiadiazolidines were converted to the corresponding 1-[2-(substituted-benzothiazolyl)-1,3-dimethyl-4-arylguanidines by their acid-catalysed rearrangement³ (Scheme 1). The structure of the compounds were determined by spectral and elemental analysis.

Results and Discussion

It was observed from the MIC values that the 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines showed more potent antifungal activity than their antibacterial activity. The antibacterial activity was in the range of 40–400 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and the antifungal activity 20–200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. The 4-ethoxy substituted derivative was the most potent in the series, inhibiting the growth of bacteria at MIC values at 40–60 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and fungi at 20–40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

- 2a: R = R' = H
b: R = 4-CH₃, R' = 6-CH₃
c: R = 4-OCH₃, R' = 6-OCH₃
d: R = 4-OC₂H₅, R' = 6-OC₂H₅
e: R = 4-COCH₃, R' = 6-COCH₃
f: R = 4-Cl, R' = 6-Cl
g: R = 4-Br, R' = 6-Br
h: R = 3-CH₃, R' = 5-CH₃
i: R = 3-OCH₃, R' = 5-OCH₃
j: R = 3-Cl, R' = 5-Cl
k: R = 2-CH₃, R' = 4-CH₃
l: R = 2-OCH₃, R' = 4-OCH₃

- 1a: R = H
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d: R = 4-OC₂H₅
e: R = 4-COCH₃
f: R = 4-Cl
g: R = 4-Br
h: R = 3-CH₃
i: R = 3-OCH₃
j: R = 3-Cl
k: R = 2-CH₃
l: R = 2-OCH₃

Scheme 1

The other noteworthy substituents were 4-Cl, 4-Br and 3-Cl which inhibited the bacteria and fungi in the range of 40–60 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Introduction of methyl group generally caused a decrease in activity as compared to the unsubstituted compound. None of the compounds were as potent as the standard drugs, i.e. miconazole (15–20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and sulphamethizole (5–6 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$).

The pattern of activity of the substituents in the benzothiazole guanidines is similar to the 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. The 4-ethoxy substituent is the most potent of all the groups tested having good antifungal activity (MIC 20–40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) against *A. niger*. It could

be a potential lead compound for further evaluation to study structure-relationship. In comparing the MIC values of 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines and benzothiazolyl guanidines, it was observed that MIC values for a particular group are generally lower in case of 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines than their corresponding benzothiazolyl guanidines. The high reactivity of ethoxy or halogenated substituents is perhaps due to their difficult metabolism. This is due to the fact that alkoxy and halogenated derivatives are metabolised by dealkylation and dehalogenation and in aromatic system removal of halogens is difficult due to resonance stabilisation.

Experimental

M.p.s were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Uv, ir (KBr) and ^1H nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded on Jasco J-0063, Perkin-Elmer 883 and Jeol Fx 90Q instruments respectively, and were consistent with the assigned structures. Elemental analysis was performed on Carlo-Ebra-Strum DP 200 instrument and the results obtained were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values. Purity of the compounds was monitored by using silica gel G (E. Merck) in benzene-methanol (80 : 20) solvent system and developed in an iodine chamber. The *N*-methyl-*N'*-arylthioureas were prepared according to the reported method⁴.

N-Methyl-*N'*-(4-methylphenylthiourea) : Methyl isothiocyanate (7.31 g, 0.1 mol) was refluxed with *p*-toluidine (10.7 g, 0.1 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) for 1 h. The solid obtained was then washed with dilute HCl and petroleum ether and crystallised from ethanol, (10.8 g, 60%), m.p. 126° (lit.⁴ 126°) (Found : N, 15.32. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ calcd for : N, 15.55).

2,4-Dimethyl-3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines : A mixture of *N*-methyl-*N'*-(4-methylphenyl)-thiourea (9.08 g, 0.05 mol) and concentrated HCl (36%, 12.9 ml), ethanol (50 ml), was added dropwise and under stirring to a solution of sodium nitrite (6.9 g, 0.1 mol) in water (25 ml). After 1h of stirring at room temperature, the precipitated sulphur was removed. The filtrate was basified with ammonia solution and the

resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol : **1h** (3.69 g, 45%), m.p. 134–37°; ν_{max} 1 615 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl_3) 6.6–7.5 (8H, m, $2 \times \text{C-CH}_2$); λ_{max} (methanol) 280 nm.

Similarly, other compounds (**1a-l**; yields 29–56%) were synthesised : **1a**, m.p. 125–27°; **c**, 133–34°; **d**, 99–101°; **e**, 105–07°; **f**, 124–26°; **g**, 134–37°; **h** 117–18°; **i**, 128–30°; **j**, 119–20°; **k**, 142–44°; **l**, 136–37°.

1-[2-(6-Methylbenzothiazolyl)]-1,3-dimethyl-4-(4-methylphenyl)guanidine (2b) : 2,4-Dimethyl-3,5-di(4-methylphenyl)imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (**1b**; 3.24 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed with HCl (50 ml, 1 mol) for 2.5 h. The contents were then basified with NaOH (1 mol) at 0°, and the resulting crude product was crystallised from ethanol, **2b** (1.46 g, 45.2%), m.p. 128–31°; ν_{max} 3 205 (NH) and 1 601 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl_3) 6.65–7.50 (8H, m, $2 \times \text{ArH}$), 5.15–5.65 (1H, bs, NH, D_2O exchangeable), 2.85 and 3.20 (6H, 2s, $2 \times \text{N-CH}_3$) and 2.15 and 2.35 (6H, 2s, $2 \times \text{C-CH}_3$); λ_{max} (methanol) 283 nm.

Similarly, other compounds (**2a-l**) were synthesised : **2a**, m.p. 119–20°; **c**, 126–27°; **d**, 111–13; **e**, 126–28; **f**, 134–35; **g**, 142–44°; **h**, 124–25°; **i**, 134–35°; **j**, 126–27; **k**, 138–40; **l**, 130–32°.

Antibacterial activity : The pure bacterial cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S.a.*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E.c.*) were obtained from Department of Microbiology, Institute of Medical Sciences, B.H.U. Nutrient broth and nutrient agar were procured from Hi media Pvt. Ltd., Bombay. Suitable dilutions of the compounds in propylene glycol were prepared in such a way that 0.1 ml of the suspension contained 20, 40, 60, 100, 150, 200, 300 and 400 μg of the compounds. MIC was determined by the plate bore method⁵. MIC of the compounds were compared with standard drug sulphamethizole.

Antifungal activity : The pure fungal strains of *Penicillium citrinum* and *Aspergillus niger* were obtained from Department of Botany, B.H.U. Suspensions of the compounds of concentrations 5, 10, 20, 40, 60, 100, 120 and 150 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ were prepared in propylene glycol. Potato dextrose agar medium was used. The

agar disc method⁶ was followed. MIC of the compounds were compared with standard drug miconazole.

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